

FUNDING FEMINIST CHANGE:
20 YEARS OF ACTION
AND SOLIDARITY
feminist review | **TRUST**

Eleanor O’Gorman

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We would like to thank the many readers who reviewed our short-listed selections in the early years of the Trust.

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Preface

The Feminist Review Trust was established over 20 years ago as a unique project: a feminist academic journal using its profits to support activist projects across the world. In that time we have funded over 180 projects and distributed over half a million pounds.

The Trust is now closing. The exigences of academic precarity and the demands placed on academics today are very different to those in place when the Trust was founded.

We do not want the Trust, its uniqueness and its contribution to the support of activist feminists to be lost. So, as part of our closure, we have commissioned two reports: one on our history and another an evaluation of our work, in the hope that others might find our experiences informative.

And, as our last political act as socialist feminists and as Trustees, we will be donating the residue of our funds to Medical Aid to Palestine to support women and children.

The Trustees of the Feminist Review Trust.
August 2024.

FUNDING FEMINIST CHANGE: TWENTY YEARS OF ACTION AND SOLIDARITY

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Many thanks to Dot Griffiths, Chair of the FRT Board, for guiding this review, not least for digging out hard copies of the archive to send in the post and soft copies via email so that the scope of the review could be ensured. To the Board members and Chair for also giving this review the space and time to engage with materials and people to build a picture of the Trust's activities and legacy. To Carrie (Hamilton) for being a supportive collaborator* as we worked on parallel yet linked tracks of the history and the learning review. And, not least, to the grantees who took the time to reflect and share their experiences of funding received from the Trust.

I would like to thank consultant Isabella Spies Agraz, based in Berlin, for her work on the visuals and graphics as well as reviewing the draft.

Eleanor O'Gorman
November 2023

*Dr. Carrie Hamilton wrote a history of the Trust 'Risk, Care and Innovation'

Introduction and Executive Summary

Background

The Feminist Review Trust commissioned this review of its work as part of a legacy and learning exercise during the winding down of its operations over 2021–2023. The Trust has been a beacon of funding to feminist projects across the UK and globally since 2001. It was registered as a charity with the UK Charity Commissioners in 2005.

Over the past 22 years, the FRT has allocated some £500,000 in small grant funding across some 188 projects, reaching across the UK, Europe, the Middle East, the USA, Latin America, Africa and Asia. The purpose of this review is to reflect and gather learning from the 20 years of grant making by the FRT. It seeks to:

- map out the range and scope of grants awarded;
- identify the types of change the grants sought to support;
- examine the unique model of a trust attached to an academic journal, and its collective ethos;
- summarise the contribution of the Trust and lessons learned from it that remain relevant for a new generation of feminist activists, funders and changemakers.

This learning review of the Trust's grant making sits alongside the history of the Trust that was commissioned at the same time and undertaken by Dr Carrie Hamilton. We have cooperated and coordinated on these outputs to document the legacy and learning from the Trust as an important focus of feminist action, both in the UK and internationally.

The following scoping themes of the review emerged from early discussions with the Board of Trustees and the Chair and initial document review:

- evolution of the mission and management of the Trust;
- governance of the trust and its unique model;
- collective work ethos and activism as a principle and practice at the Trust;
- the expectations and type of change created at the level of the Trust itself and at the level of projects;
- legacy and lessons for feminist funding and action today.

A mix of methods was used to inform the research and report, including:

- desk-top review of database and available documents for 48 funded projects;
- group discussion with Board members at outset and early drafting stages;
- individual interviews with Board members (11) and selected grantees (4);
- in-person briefings and discussions on emerging draft findings.¹

¹ See Annex 1 for list of project documents consulted. See Annexes 2 and 3 for list of interviews conducted and guiding questions.

Summary of Lessons from the Review

1. The Feminist Review Trust, with relatively modest funds of GBP £500,000 over 20 years, supported an impressive range of 188 projects across multiple thematic areas both in the UK and around the world.
2. The largest area of thematic support was Violence against Women & Girls, making up 18% of the projects. Other major themes included: Arts & Culture, Migrant & Refugee Women (14% and 13% respectively); Running Feminist Groups/Centres, Health-related Projects (9% and 8%); Abortion and Sexual & Reproductive Rights (7%); Memory, Narratives, & Oral Histories (6%). Smaller but still distinct themes continued with Women with Disabilities, Justice Processes & Systems, Education, Peace & Conflict Responses, Environment & Climate Change and Feminist Economic Analysis.
3. The types of change enabled by Feminist Review Trust funding can be categorised as:
 - changes that were *catalytic* in terms of pump priming or paving the way for larger changes or for wider support to a project the Trust had funded;
 - changes ensuring the *survival* of a group or initiative, as part of the rationale for emergency support to prevent it from dying/failing, or to help it address a difficulty;
 - changes aimed at the *sustainability* of projects, i.e. ensuring they would last beyond the funding of the Trust or contribute to longer-term change processes.
4. The projects funded around the world by the Feminist Review Trust may seem like drops in the ocean, but each one is an inspiring story of solidarity and support to women acting together in some part of the world to change, improve and celebrate their lives. This too is a form of movement building.
5. The energy, dedication, professionalism, and persistence of the Collective - and the activist labour of the Trust members - are key to the Feminist Review Trust's success, and distinguish it as a grant maker.
6. The foundations of the FRT were laid by an innovative profit-sharing deal negotiated by the Feminist Review Collective with the journal publishers which provided a funding pipeline for the Trust's feminist grant making. This meant it was not in the immediate position of having to raise funds, build an endowment, or seek legacies and other sources of finance in order to sustain a funding pool.
7. The delay in gaining charitable status until 2005 from the UK Charity Commissioners was partly a question of how feminist funding and projects were often perceived as

‘too political’ and how civil society space is defined or constrained by such official processes. These are concerns that echo today.

8. The Trust’s commitment to funding ‘hard-to-fund’ projects raises important questions about what feminist funding is for, and what constitutes a funding risk in a context where individuals, groups, communities and organisations are making positive change in the lives of women.
9. Despite the apparent growth of feminist and gender-related funds supported by governments, private philanthropists or public fundraising, feminist funding remains as fragile and precarious as it ever was for grassroots groups.
10. In the UK, the impact of austerity policies post-2010 is reflected in the rising applications from services to vulnerable women affected by budget cuts. This raised for the Trust tensions and sharpened dilemmas about the impossibility of plugging service gaps on this scale and how far ‘sticking-plaster’ support would help.
11. Feminist grant making is not only about value for money, sustainability or even results, although these hallmarks of contemporary monitoring, evaluation and learning are important in terms of accountability for monies spent, and for measuring the intended change and impact effected by the funding. What can be lost, however, are the creative, organic change processes that a relatively small fund, run by a group of dedicated activists, can achieve when reaching out and deliberately funding grassroots events, programmes, initiatives and groups that would not necessarily come under the purview of a fully professionalised fund.

1. Overview of Funding and Projects by the FRT, 2003–2021

This review looks at 177 projects funded during 2003–2021, selected from the final 188 funded by the Trust until it ceased funding in 2023.² Of a total of 163 grants where location was identified, 75 were awarded across the UK, with a global spread of 88 further projects (see Table 1, p 4). The support ranged in financial terms from £300 to £15,000 per award. Many were one-off allocations.

A breakdown of fifteen areas of support or themes is provided in Table 1. The overall total of 207 projects reflects the fact some of the 177 funded projects addressed more than one theme. The thematic analysis allocated each project more than one label if it addressed different themes. This reflects the intersectionality of many of the projects in terms of

² The Trust has funded 11 other projects since the January 2021 allocations, taking it up to March 2022. All applications and funding decisions had ceased as of 2022. The 177 projects considered by the review can be found on the website <https://www.feminist-review-trust.com/awards/>

embracing many participants and promoting inclusivity as well as reflecting the varied activities and services offered by the groups and organisations of the grantees.

Thematic areas	Projects funded with this theme
Violence against Women & Girls	36
Arts & Culture	28
Migrant & Refugee Women	27
Running Feminist Groups/Centres	18
Health-focused Projects	17
Abortion and Sexual & Reproductive Rights	15
Memory, Narratives, & Oral Histories	13
Women with Disabilities	9
Economy & Work	8
Education-focused Projects	7
Justice Processes & Systems	7
Journalism & Media	7
Peace & Conflict	6
Sex Workers	6
Environment & Climate Change	3
Total	207

Table 1 – Overview of thematic areas and projects funded

Figure 1 expresses this breakdown of themes in the form of a pie chart showing the relative percentage of coverage in terms of an overall 100%. The real number of projects funded stays at 177. Nevertheless, an intersectional approach allowed us to allocate more than one thematic area to a funded project; for example, women with disabilities could also be categorized within a health-focused project. Thus, while the budget stays consistent, this categorization allowed the FRT to reach 207 thematic areas, adding up to a growth of 53% in the value of projects reached. Hence, the pie chart incorporates 207 projects to demonstrate that the money going into the 177 projects funded allowed for a broader incorporation of thematic areas, creating even greater impact.

Figure 1 – Thematic Breakdown of FRT – funded projects

Figure 2 – A global map of FRT-funded projects

Location	Number of grants given
<i>Africa</i>	16
Cameroon	1
DRC	2
Ethiopia	1
Eswatini (formerly Swaziland)	1
Gambia	2
Ghana	1
Kenya	1
South Africa	3
Uganda	2
Zimbabwe	2
<i>Middle East and North Africa</i>	12
Israel/Palestine	4
Jordan	1
Lebanon	1
Syria	2
Turkey	4
<i>Asia</i>	12
Bangladesh	1
India	3
Kyrgyzstan	2
Nepal	1
Pakistan	1
Philippines	1
Sri Lanka	2
<i>Europe</i>	28
Albania	1
Bosnia and Herzegovina	3
Bulgaria	1
Georgia	2
Greece	2
Ireland	3
Italy	1
Lithuania	1
Macedonia	1
Montenegro	1
Poland	4
Romania	3
Spain	3
Ukraine	2

<i>Latin America and Caribbean</i>	17
Argentina	7
Colombia	1
Cuba	2
Ecuador	2
Mexico	2
Peru	1
Trinidad and Tobago	2
USA	
USA	3
Houston, Texas	1
Berkeley, California	1
USA-wide	1
United Kingdom	
<i>United Kingdom</i>	75
UK-wide scope	19
London	15
England-wide scope	1
England and Wales scope	1
North of England – Yorkshire, Leeds, York, Sheffield	6
Newcastle-upon-Tyne, Tyneside	3
Northwest – Merseyside, Liverpool	2
Manchester	3
East Midlands, Leicester	2
Lincoln	1
Derbyshire	1
West Midlands, Birmingham	2
Coventry	1
Warwickshire	1
East of England – Bedfordshire	2
Essex	2
West England – Bristol	2
South East England – Sussex	4
Scotland-wide	1
Edinburgh	2
Glasgow	2
Orkney	1
Northern Ireland – Fermanagh	1

Table 2 – Regional and country breakdown of grants awarded

Analysis of Project Themes

The largest area of support funded by the FRT was *Violence against Women & Girls*, making up 18% of the projects with some 36 projects supported. Actions included retraining of female genital mutilation (FGM) practitioners in The Gambia; supporting materials for Women's Aid in Orkney; campaigning on sexual violence against young women in Poland; support to a new London Violence against Women & Girls Consortium; addressing street harassment in Edinburgh; education and empowerment of young people (15–22) in Ukraine, and materials to support work on changing attitudes towards honour killings in Pakistan.

Following close behind in second and third places were the themes of *Arts & Culture* (14%), and *Migrant & Refugee Women* (13%).

Twenty-eight Arts & Culture projects took various forms:

- *Theatre productions* – dissemination of a play on women migrants; education packs for outreach on a play on violence against women; support to a theatre group performing plays on the experiences of women during WW1; arts and advocacy workshops through the medium of an opera about and involving sex workers.
- *Public art murals as advocacy*, made by domestic workers in Mexico and feminist campaigns in Sarajevo.
- Feminist *media project* involving artists exploring dis/ability in Lithuania.
- Support to setting up a *feminist art studio* in Tbilisi, Georgia; support to Ladyfest Brighton festival, 'a multi-media festival – with art, music, film, dance, and workshops – to showcase the talent and vision of female and queer artists and to raise money for women's charities'.
- Creation of a feminist and anti-racist *walking tour* in Barcelona by the activist women of Sindihogar (Independent Trade Union of Cleaning and Care Workers).
- *Film making, documentary making and screenings* – equipment for free film-making course in Glasgow aimed at women of colour and trans people (Digital Desperados); film screenings event in York on gender identities; feminist film festival & workshops in Bristol; support to film screenings by local filmmakers at Ladyfest Birmingham. Documentaries on women's lives in migration (Bangladesh and Ethiopia); sexual violence in conflict, updating of *A Place of Rage* (by Kali Films) including interviews with Angela Davis, June Jordan and Alice Walker; documenting stories of abortion debates in Trinidad and Tobago. Support to screenwriters in Cuba.
- *Music-related projects* included the ethics of zine archiving (self-published, self-created art, words, sounds, and how they are considered in an 'archive') and support to female punk music zine, as well as projects supporting women in the UK music industry via technology and music, and cyberfeminism.

Twenty-seven projects aimed at *Migrant & Refugee Women* included:

- support to Asylum Aid to promote Charter of Rights of Women Seeking Asylum;
- a sanctuary garden project in London;
- Yarl's Wood Befrienders and research on fast-track process and bail in the UK;
- Eastern European women in Essex;
- Syrian refugee women in Lebanon, Jordan and Edinburgh;
- Afghan women in the UK;
- women refugees and asylum seekers in Liverpool;
- domestic violence hotline for Polish women in the UK;
- Women's Therapy Centre in London, to support 100 women refugees and asylum seekers;
- Lesbian Immigration Support Group in Manchester;
- newly arrived young women in East London, offering language skills and social support to overcome isolation;
- LGBTQI-led project in Turkey, including refugee communities;
- data and advocacy on asylum policy in Italy;
- Crimean women asylum seekers in Ukraine.

The fourth and fifth largest thematic areas were *Running Feminist Groups/Centres* (9%) and *Health-related Projects* (8%)

Feminist Group funding included:

- feminist ecological summer camp in Poland providing a range of classes and skills training;
- a new type of feminist and anti-racist consortium on VAWG bringing together 22 organisations across London;
- Fawcett Society, London – work on increasing women's political participation and representation in the UK (3 grants);
- Centre for Women and Democracy – research on localism bill and other legislation and implications for women's representation in economic and political decision-making (2011);
- Rights of Women – legal advice for women on family law, survivors of sexual violence.

Health-related projects included mental health support; NAZ project in London on research into BME and sexuality; healthy living for disadvantaged women; breastfeeding peer support for mothers; affordable period products through the manufacture of sanitary napkins; menopause research; schoolgirls' health and self-esteem; breaking taboos about women living with HIV/AIDS, and skills for health workers to help prevent unsafe abortions.

A significant cluster of 15 projects was funded by the Trust over 20 years in the area of

Abortion and Sexual & Reproductive Rights. These supported, among others:

- fortieth anniversary campaign material and events for the Pro-Choice Campaign in the UK, marking the legalisation of abortion in the UK in 1967, and support to a postcard campaign to defend time limits;
- advocacy and legal change in Argentina, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Poland and Romania;
- ‘Respect My Choice’ campaign in Trinidad and Tobago;
- support network for Irish women coming to the UK to seek abortions when it was illegal in Ireland;
- skills training to support young people on Education for Choice in UK;
- sexual and reproductive rights of women with intellectual disabilities in Romania;
- contraceptive autonomy and education in a joint Israeli/Palestinian project;
- reproductive health education for marginalised women in the Philippines.

Another significant cluster of projects addressed the theme of *Memory, Narratives, & Oral Histories* (6%), with 13 projects found to promote such methodologies for activism. These included:

- Black feminist oral histories in the UK;
- LGBTQ herstories in Bosnia and Herzegovina;
- domestic workers in Mexico;
- Sylvia Pankhurst website in the UK;
- oral histories of menopause through mass observation directive, inviting survey respondents (women and men) to add information on midlife transitions;
- lives and stories of lesbians in Cuba;
- narratives of honour killings in Pakistan.

Smaller numbers of projects addressed other distinct themes: *Women with Disabilities* (9 Projects), *Justice Processes & Systems*³ (7 projects), *Education-focused Projects* (7 projects), *Peace & Conflict Responses* (6 projects) and *Environment & Climate Change* (3 projects).

Of further note is the support the Trust gave to *feminist economic analysis* to underpin the visibility of female labour and the impact of government policies. This included work by the Women’s Budget Group (UK) on analysis of budgets, and support to women advocates living in poverty to enable them to lobby politicians. Homeworkers Worldwide ran a North of England research project on informal and precarious work, while on a global level there was support to a project on the rights of women flower workers in global supply chains.

³ This included a pre-trial detention project in Mexico awarded in July 2020, one of the few projects funded at the higher end of the range at £14,320.

Women's livelihoods were another dimension of the *Economy & Work theme*. Projects supported included skills training in Lebanon, e-banking and exchange of skills, employment and business coaching for disadvantaged women, farming livelihoods for women living with HIV/AIDS in rural Kenya, skills training for women in woodwork in Eswatini, a dairy project for Dalit women in India and biomass fuel briquettes in Uganda to produce community fuel.

This range and reach of projects funded by the Feminist Review Trust is all the more impressive when one considers that the grant allocation and management system underpinning it was delivered by unpaid, activist labour.

2. Management of Funding Decisions and Grants

What to fund?

The foundations of the FRT were laid by means of an innovative profit-sharing deal negotiated by the Feminist Review Collective with the publishers of the *Feminist Review* journal. This meant that the allocation of funds to the Trust would be regular and could be anticipated and managed. This is not to say that the flow of funds was constant or fixed, but the deal effectively provided a funding pipeline for the Trust's feminist grant making and meant it was not in the immediate position of having to raise funds, build an endowment, or seek legacies and other sources of sustaining a funding pool.

It was this funding base that enabled the Trust to focus its energies on implementing its feminist values by encouraging applications from a diversity of groups and organisations and ensuring an approach where 'every application was read and reviewed'. This is very unusual and rarely possible even with funds that have full-time paid and professional staff who work with grassroots funding.

As an overall observation, the review found the administration, documentation of Board meetings, projects and budgets to be of an excellent standard, thorough and structured. The online grant database on the website is very transparent and informative. It sets out the grants awarded over two or three cycles of funding every year from April 2003 until March 2022. A summary of each project and the amount granted are recorded, with website links to the grantee where available. The Charity Commission's website notes that reporting by FRT 'is up to date and on time' as of March 2023.

There is scope for strengthening the archiving of documents for accessibility. Email requests met with provision of a good spread of projects over the 20 years, both in scanned documents from older awards and soft copies for more recent ones. However, there is a significant cache of documents that is currently on one computer archive with some copies available through other Trustees. The Board is negotiating with Archivists at the London School of Economics

Library to include the Feminist Review Trust archive in the Women's Library holding. This will ensure that a selection of the archive as well as the website is available to researchers and interested persons in the future.

The process of grant application was straightforward and relatively simple, with a short, clear form including a 100-word summary of the application, a detailed description of the project (not more than 1,000 words) and a short reply on follow-up to funding and sustainability. The ease and accessibility of the application form and correspondence with FRT is a point echoed by the interviews with grantees and in the reporting on projects.

The interviews with grantees highlighted the following reflections on the experience of applying to and engaging with the Trust:

- Grantees learned of the Trust from other feminist researchers and activists or were already very familiar with the *Feminist Review* journal and learned that the Trust was an extension/creation of that.
- The 'difficult-to-fund' criterion was mentioned as a draw; it felt like an invitation to apply that was rarely offered. Permission was given for even a seedling idea or an unexciting activity such as coordination to be brought to the table.
- The application process was easy and simple – 'the money just arrived'.
- There was less burden on grantees as regards reporting, but still a framework of accountability.
- Validation from an external funder leveraged and influenced the grantees' next applications to other funders.
- There was a sense of solidarity and 'not being alone' in addressing an issue; grantees felt both seen and heard.
- The fact that seed funding could enable great change was a welcome surprise.
- The risk appetite of the Trust was relatively high, inviting trust and discussion.

The criteria guiding the selection and shortlisting processes evolved over time and through practice. What emerges from the review is a guiding sense of 'funding hard-to-fund projects', to support feminist action that would otherwise struggle to get support. An official list of the criteria emerged as the Trust sought to streamline, improve and share its selection and decision-making regarding projects. The minutes of a strategy meeting by the Board in March 2021 summarised the guiding criteria as follows:

- Feminist profile
- Risk profile
- Fraud potential
- Budget – who benefits?
- Exemplar – for dissemination
- Sustainability
- 'Bang for buck'

- Other funding possibilities

Reading minutes from the Board meetings over the years, it is clear that concern about how best to fund and what to fund featured often in discussions, notably in defining projects as feminist projects or women's projects in terms of ambition for change. This speaks to the Trust's scope and ambition for change. From the interviews with Trustees certain phrases recur as to the types of projects that were selected: for instance, 'hard-to-fund' projects – ones that would not easily get funding from elsewhere but were considered worth doing on their own merits and assessed risks – and 'sticking-plaster projects', a phrase referring to keeping projects or organisations going until they could get more funding.

A non-profit website called Philanthropy Circuit, which aims to strengthen philanthropy in Africa, provides information on funding calls and lists the Feminist Review Trust.⁴ It describes the funding scope of FRT as focusing on two criteria: (1) hard-to-fund projects, and (2) 'pump-priming, interventionist projects which support feminist values'. The description gives a helpful expansion on what 'hard-to-fund' means.

Some types of projects are difficult to fund. Typically, these projects have no other obvious sources of funding. This might mean, for example, that traditional academic sources are either not interested in the area or that it is an activist project or that it is too feminist for most conventional funding sources.

The pump-priming projects are described as including training and development projects, one-off events, etc.

Discussions with Trustees revealed that some of the very early grants were made to academic researchers disseminating or publishing feminist research, and that a conscious decision was made not to continue down this route. It was felt that other sources were available for research and that the limited funds of the Trust could be consumed very quickly in this way. More feminist action projects addressing feminist change and ideas in practice were encouraged. This did not exclude the Trust from funding specific conferences or events that promoted or brought together researchers and activists around specific themes, as set out in the project overview above.

What was surprising was to discover that *all* applications were read, reviewed and considered in the shortlisting process. To give perspective on the unpaid effort this involved, interviews reveal that in some years there could be 1,500 applications and just 12 or so awards to be granted across the three cycles. The shortlists could include 150 projects to be further whittled down. Two of the Board members took the lead on the final shortlisting after the first selection had been made based on a distribution of the applications to a wider group of Board members. Some Trustees recalled reading as many as 50 applications in this first round.

⁴ <https://philanthropycircuit.org/grant/call-for-proposals/feminist-review-trust-grant-program/>

Yet, alongside the many 'hard-to-fund' projects, there are examples of funding given to relatively well-established NGOs where there was a feminist theory of change at work but where the added value or distinctive contribution of the Trust was not immediately obvious. There is a risk that small strategic funding may be lost among other donations from large NGOs, government, or philanthropic foundations. This can be difficult to discern without a fuller conversation at the time with the grantees and how the grant was viewed. For example, a review of Fawcett Society reporting and correspondence to the Trust, discussed below (p. 24) in the context of core funding, demonstrates that in fact the FRT grant was critical during a challenging time for the organisation and in the run-up to the 2010 general election in the UK.

One strong observation from the interviews and experience of the Board members was that the grapevine of feminist activists and organisations is clearly very strong and vibrant. This was evidenced by the fact that when certain themes were funded and listed on the website, similar applications for those themes would appear in the next cycle. For example, if domestic violence projects received funding, the next cycle would see a spike of applications from similar projects. The impression that emerges is that clusters would form around themes at a certain period and successful grantees would share with others in their networks. The Trust sought to address this via its communications and the website and to insist that the trust was open to many areas of action and interest.

A sense emerges of

- (1) a healthy appetite for risk in seeking to fund 'hard-to-fund' projects and one-off allocations;
- (2) a wish not to burden grantees with heavy processes of application and reporting, while having systems and accountability for funding and decision-making.

The success of this approach is borne out by the rigorous keeping of accounts and good accounting practices, and the very high number of reports completed, as well as the feedback and documentation available. Where the burden did lie was on the collective labour of Trustees in reviewing assessing and shortlisting applications.

Follow-up and learning during implementation

Follow-up, accompaniment, and learning received less emphasis overall. The 'heavy lifting' was carried out in the application and selection processes. The strengthening of the follow-up phase was much helped by one Trustee taking a focused and structured approach to follow-up with grantees, once funds were allocated.

The actions and learning of the Trust on follow-up included the following:

- Regular updates and discussions were held at Trustee meetings on reports and issues for funded projects.
- One Board member took on a key role in emailing, following up and introducing a more systematic approach in later years of the Trust. Email exchanges with some grantees demonstrate this follow-up process.
- It proved difficult to trace back the progress as time lapsed, even after three years when this was attempted by the Trust.
- The challenge of follow-up affects archiving and tracking; however, there is a repository of hard copies and online copies of the projects.
- Trustees did not know that the programme would reach the scale it did – it grew organically.

Longer-term follow-up and learning about a project's impact is time-consuming and requires dedicated resources that a voluntary trust often cannot commit, given the relatively modest size of the grants. There was an effort at one point to conduct a follow-up exercise after three years, but it was difficult to get responses. Given that many of the organisations and initiatives were one-off or volunteer local efforts, this is perhaps not surprising. It is not impossible, of course, to find ways and systems to achieve this kind of follow-up, but it requires investment and focus that would be hard to justify for a Trust distributing small amounts of money to many organisations, groups and individuals.

For example, online free or low-cost communications via Zoom, Skype, WhatsApp, etc. make it possible today to consider active follow-up and engagement that was not possible 20 years ago. One could imagine today how easy it would be to have short videos created via smartphones by participants of projects from anywhere. Also, it would have been good to consider recruiting a volunteer or Trustee who would lead on learning, or to team up with schools or colleges to conduct such exercises. Ideas are easy to generate but, without persistent follow-up and some financial resources, can be hard to put into practice.

Very correctly and commendably, the clear actions and intentions of the Trust have always been to allocate and distribute the funds as widely as possible to grassroots feminist actions, and the core labour of the Trust to achieve this aim has been activist, non-stipendiary and collective. This level of integrity and input of time, effort, labour and expertise involved in creating the Trust's ethos is key to its success. How to replicate, adapt, or reimagine this for a new generation of feminist funding and change is one of the main challenges thrown up by this learning review.

The end-of-project reports (called 'award reports') provide rich and articulate data and examples in many cases of the achievements of the projects, any adaptations that were made or challenges faced. Some include photographs, website links, sample outputs (leaflets, agendas, advice publications etc.), and receipts.

Visibility and credit for FRT funding was mentioned on acceptance forms and the final reports by grantees. Examples can be found even now on the Roshni Sindh website in Pakistan; the inserts and bookplates placed in feminist, women-centred books distributed to academic and public libraries across Zimbabwe; the high-profile acknowledgement of the books and reports of the Magdalene Justice project, which have international reach and interest; and the large number of order forms for the Rights of Women publications for free dissemination of legal advice books on immigration, housing and violence against women, and targeted to BME and asylum seeker women.

3. *The Engine of Collective Activism and Labour*

The energy, dedication, professionalism, and persistence of the collective labour of the Feminist Review Trust are key to its success and distinguish it as a grant maker. It is an activist-led and managed Trust with no paid staff or fundraising team. The details of the grant-making process over three funding cycles every year reflect the scale of input required by the Board of Trustees in reviewing and shortlisting applications and maintaining the structured calendar of meetings, minutes, decision-making, follow-up and reporting.

This dedicated and active engagement of the Trustees in reviewing, shortlisting and ultimate decision-making about allocations is a very commendable feature of what can be termed engaged and collective leadership. Core to this are the regular and transparent discussions about project selection, updating and troubleshooting. One Trustee declared ‘our money was important even if it was £350’ – there was a sense of being conscientious and transparent in deciding what to fund and ensuring it was spent well. This sense of probity was instilled by the Chair and filtered through discussions and decision-making.

In any collective endeavour, certain individuals act as leaders even though there can be discomfort for some to be named as such. However, it was clear to this reviewer, and reaffirmed by interviews with Trustees, that the Chair has to a great extent been a driver throughout the lifetime of the Trust, as one of the initial founders emerging from the *Feminist Review* Collective. She has also played a large part in assuring ongoing income from the original publishing deal that she helped negotiate, and in establishing the financial management systems and keeping a hand on the tiller to ensure the overall effective running of the Trust. What is unique in this long-standing leadership role is that these personal leadership strengths were embedded in a commitment to, and practice of, collective action and leadership by the Board of Trustees.

This collective activism led to systems and labour that built and managed a professional grant-making operation. One can speak of an ‘ethics of feminist activism’ that shaped this evolution. As one Trustee remarked, ‘It was a political project. We had a sense of ourselves as the activist arm to an academic journal.’

A 2015 article by Marina Warner⁵ describes well the changing state of academic labour even after a generation of women academics in the UK and internationally had striven to overcome significant inequalities and prejudices in order to gain tenure, research funding, publications and positions. That battle for a new and diverse generation of women and LGBTQI academics and research continues and shapes in part the pressures on the unique and original model of the *Feminist Review* Collective and the FRT. This model provides a resourced example of feminist theory and practice – a rare praxis emerging from the challenges of feminism to the academy.

The FRT model relies on activist labour, which has become more tightly squeezed in the precarious and pressured economy and is also affected by changes in academia, from where many of the original drivers of the Trust emerged. Such changes include poor contracts, pressure to publish and to take on greater workloads, and inroads upon family and caring arrangements. This makes it financially precarious and difficult to carve out time at the scale needed to run a funding process such as that of the FRT.

Changeover in Board membership and recruitment of younger and diverse members was ongoing but could possibly have begun earlier in the lifetime of the Trust. The sustainability of the Trust's funding was challenged by decisions taken by the *Feminist Review* Collective that the funds allocated to the Trust needed to be taken back into the journal and used to support academic work by members.⁶

Both the recruitment of new and younger Trustees and the decision of the *Feminist Review* Collective to cease allocating funds to the Trust point to a new context and politics affecting the collective action and academic engagement that were hallmarks of the Trust from its origins. The growing insecurity of career progression, contracts and pay in academia, alongside wider economic pressures affecting the ability of younger people to take up unpaid activist labour and leadership responsibilities, are not just contributing factors for the Trust but a trend that affects many not-for-profit organisations and initiatives. For example, even within academia the unseen and assumed labour of peer review and editing journals have contributed to challenges for higher education and for researchers and academics seeking to forge a viable career.

This decline in activist collective labour is also a challenge for many of the grantees, and a valid question can be posed as to how small feminist projects can survive or adapt in such a climate. In seeking to diversify boards, encourage intergenerational change and leadership, and promote active community engagement, funders may want and need to reflect more

⁵ 'Learning My Lesson: Marina Warner on the disfiguring of higher education', *TLS* 37, 6 (March 2015). I am grateful to Irene Stanton of Weaver Press, Zimbabwe (FRT grantee) for sharing this reference.

⁶ The *Feminist Review* Collective was approached for an interview as part of the learning review but no reply was received up to the time of completing this report.

deeply on the obstacles and enablers for such collective labour and participation in movements and projects for improving social and other outcomes.

4. *Feminist Change and Movement Building by FRT*

The tagline on the FRT website reads, 'supporting projects that transform the lives of women'. This review found assumptions of different kinds of change across the projects. While explicit theories of change are not advanced, the short application template invited a description of what might be achieved with the grant. Three types of change were identified from the criteria used for selection and the reporting by grantees:

- changes that would be *catalytic* in terms of pump priming or paving the way for larger changes or for wider support to a project FRT has funded;
- changes that would ensure the *survival* of a group or initiative, as part of the rationale for emergency support to prevent it from dying/failing, or to help it address difficulty;
- changes aimed at the *sustainability* of the projects considered, i.e. at ensuring they would last beyond the funding of the Trust or contribute to longer-term change processes.

The review also found in some earlier cycles of grants, a clustering of traditional skills training projects more likely to occur in community-based development aid NGOs. The aim, in terms of reaching rural women in countries such as India or Uganda and supporting training for livelihoods skills fits well with the aims of the Trust. However, in some cases a specifically feminist or empowerment-based theory of change seemed to be less present than in other project descriptions where the language is more everyday and focused on setting out how the change would impact on equality, income or changes in laws to improve the lives of women.

Case study

The Irish Magdalenes in the UK: A Restorative Justice Project, from 2011, demonstrates just one of the trajectories of impact that can be hard to trace for a small grant once time has passed. Justice for Magdalenes Research was awarded £7,287 by the FRT in September 2011, as a response to the emerging stories of historic abuse and forced labour of women and girls in homes and laundries run by religious orders in Ireland. The project summary on the database for 2011 describes the following context:

Many survivors who were released made their home in the UK, often fearing re-incarceration should they remain in Ireland; it is these women who will provide the testimonies as part of this project. The ultimate goal is to contribute to understanding the lives of women who lived in the Magdalene institutions. There is currently no reliable information on even basic data such as how many women were committed to these institutions and how many survivors still remain in Ireland, the UK and in countries such as the USA. These UK survivor testimonies are a crucial part of a larger oral history which seeks to collect participants' and eye-witnesses' accounts of the Magdalene institutions in the Justice for Magdalenes campaign to seek restorative justice for these institutionalised women from the Irish State and the Catholic Church.

An interview was conducted with Prof. Katherine O'Donnell of University College Dublin, who co-led this project at the time. She said the group learned of the Trust from the *Feminist Review* journal and described the process as 'an easy application' with 'a quick answer'. The grant provided a 'direct injection of cash' to the project 'with no strings attached'. It was 'immensely valuable' and made sure one person on the project could be paid, with travel costs to enable her to go around and collect the testimonies, as time was tight given the need to drive the wider campaign for a state apology and state reparations. 'I was parsimonious in handing it out', she recalled.

The small team at Justice for Magdalenes (JFM) were 'emboldened by the FRT grant to apply to the Irish Research Council' for funding and were successful. The FRT funding acted as a calling card, evidence of external support that helped leverage other funding. 'It gave credibility and showed the viability and feasibility of our project, as the pilot project had achieved a lot'. The funding helped with the challenge of 'getting our own institutions to take us seriously'. It also meant a lot that it was feminist funding coming from outside Ireland, giving JFM a sense of international solidarity. O'Donnell said that 'what looks like a small amount of money, meant the world to us'. Such small grants can also help do a lot, as there is no administrative burden and they can directly fund the grantee's core work or (in this case) the gathering of oral testimonies to build evidence for justice and reparations.

In June 2011 the Irish government had announced the establishment of an Inter-Departmental Committee on the Magdalene Laundries. The JFM had lobbied for this and had also launched an oral history project to support survivors and ensure they were part of the truth-telling process, as well as establishing cases for reparations. The oral history project set the basis for the collection of testimonies with clear protocols so survivors would not face recounting their experience and evidence more than once. It was an international collaborative effort involving various researchers and universities in different jurisdictions, notably Ireland, the UK, and the US. O'Donnell notes that the risk of failure for them was very high at all points in terms of getting justice. However, the final report by the Magdalene Laundries Committee in 2013, after some initial political stalling, led to a state apology to survivors from the Government of Ireland and a visit to the UK by the Irish Taoiseach to meet with survivors in the UK. A government scheme was then established to make reparations, and consultations continued with survivors on this.

Today there is a remembrance and memorialisation project around this history, with the testimonies at its heart, on a new website named Justice For Magdalenes Research. A critically acclaimed book on the campaign for justice, published in 2021 by the team behind the oral history project, gives acknowledgement to the early funding by FRT: 'We are pleased to acknowledge the *Feminist Review* Trust for an early grant to conduct a pilot study of the Magdalene Oral History Project and the Irish Research Council for further funding which allowed for an invaluable collection of Magdalene survivors' voices to emerge.' Prof. O'Donnell remarked in our interview that 'we will always be crediting the Feminist Review Trust'. The oral histories are still being gathered and there are over 100 in the archive.

The unknown threads woven by the support to the Magdalene survivors that were traced above can be seen in random, human ways in other grants. For example, in April 2004, in one of the earlier awards made by the Trust, a young PhD graduate was given a grant of £1000 to 'attend two conferences to disseminate her research work on Chinese women and economic restructuring'. I looked her up and discovered Dr Jieyu Liu is now Reader in Sociology of China and Deputy Director of the SOAS China Institute at SOAS University of London, where she leads ongoing research on rapid demographic and social changes in contemporary China. Another early recipient of support from the FRT in 2003 is Prof. Aisha Gill, a leading criminologist, advocate, author and expert on violence against women, whose influence stretches across academic research, policy-making and legal advice. Her early grant was to disseminate her doctoral research on South Asian women and domestic violence.

The point here is that synergies which may take years to play out, or which emerge and may never be traced or reported, nonetheless remain valid. It is the promise and potential of these synergies that fired up the engine of small grant making at FRT. There are many threads one

would like to pull and follow from the tapestry of funding that the FRT has woven over 20 years.

There is a plethora of one-off projects where the follow-up may not be known because (a) the project ended for tragic or unavoidable reasons; (b) the time and cost of learning and following up are too great to be justified by the size of the grant but are given with goodwill and in most cases result in a short report on what has happened, and that is the end of the impact journey; (c) the sheer number of small grants makes it difficult, without additional resources, to undertake a learning review in a timely and recurring manner. Yet the sense is that, even where longer-term impact reviews are not possible, we can gather insights into the short-term achievement of grants, and that the provision of small grants enabling events or activities is a feminist action in itself and is successful at that level. It is considered good enough that a plan has been presented and an event requiring a small amount of funding has occurred. The ripples outward from the action may be none or may be many but are simply not known.

Feminist Movement Building

It is interesting to reflect on what FRT as a feminist funder has meant for feminist movement building throughout its 20 years of activity. As we consider the range of projects funded around the world by the FRT, many may seem like drops in the ocean, but each project is an inspiring story of solidarity and support shown to women acting together in some part of the world to change, improve and celebrate their lives. This too is a form of movement building, not least by:

- small-scale funding that many donors would consider too high a transaction cost to roll out;
- funding beyond registered charities and established groups to reach many local groups, communities and individuals that would not otherwise get access to resources for projects;
- inspiring the leaders of these projects to continue their work and letting them know they are validated and seen by a fund and by women from outside their locality;
- leveraging credibility and resources by enabling some projects to advance work, pilot ideas, and/or gather evidence that enables them to win support from larger foundations and government bodies;
- enabling one-off events and activities that in themselves are meaningful in documenting lives; gathering women together for shared events, planning, support, and building a movement in small, localised, organic and incremental ways;
- showing up and shoring up the holes in critical services for women and girls across the UK, caused in large part by UK government's austerity approach to public service spending since 2010.

Furthermore, we can consider that the FRT has been an important systemic actor in the UK and has demonstrated solidarity and allyship in other countries and regions with feminist organisations and projects. This is evidenced by (1) the scale of projects when taken as a whole; (2) the willingness of FRT to provide core funding in some cases; (3) the alignment of the FRT with organisations that grew out of 1970s/1980s feminist activism and research; (4) the FRT's direct support to convening networks and groups and bolstering the feminist ecosystem.

The emergence and growth of the FRT synchronised with a range of pioneering feminist-inspired organisations that emerged during the 1970s to 1990s. These include:

- Southall Black Sisters (1979) – carving new action and space for feminism and anti-racism and combating violence against women;
- the Women's Budget Group (1989) – driving research, analysis, and advocacy on gender, public financing, and policies addressing inequality through a lens of feminist economics;
- the Women's Therapy Centre (1976–2019) – championing access to psychotherapy for vulnerable women;
- the Women's Environmental Network (1989) – advocating on the gender-related impacts of climate change and the need for greater participation of women in pursuing environmental justice. Based in East London with advocacy reach nationwide.

These organisations grew from activism by women for women and with allies.

In some cases, the FRT gave core funding support to maintain this feminist fabric. Sometimes it was to keep an organisation or programme running. Notable examples include the Abortion Support Network, the Fawcett Society, the Women's Therapy Centre, and the Lesbian Immigration Support Group (LISG).

The Feminist Review Trust grant will pay for our core work for one year. It will also allow us the opportunity to develop our group and establish other income streams for us to become more self-sustaining. (LISG project document)

In July 2010, a letter to the Trust from the then CEO of the Fawcett Society is a good example of 'plugging a gap' or ensuring that an important plan of action could be continued in an emergency:

A huge thank you to the Feminist Review Trust for stepping up in a time of crisis at the Fawcett Society and making a grant of £2,000 to facilitate our work to promote equality of opportunity with specific focus on women's economic rights during the downturn and ensuring we could continue to deliver a tight plan of action to maintain the profile of women's inequalities in the run-up to the 2010 general election.

This work included the election campaign *What About Women?*, involving a coalition of 60 different organisations, and the *Equal Pay, where next?* conference celebrating the 40th anniversary of the Equal Pay Act in cooperation with trade unions. The letter went on to describe how the FRT ‘plugged a funding gap at a critical time’ alongside other funders, including the Joseph Rowntree Charitable Trust, which is well respected for its work on poverty and inequality in the UK as part of its wider remit.

Some interviewees argue that supporting feminist and women’s organisations is itself a necessary contribution to maintaining an ecosystem for advocacy, action and transformation of women’s lives. Thus, the above-mentioned contributions to Southall Black Sisters, the Fawcett Society and the Women’s Budget Group, for example, shored up core work in the areas of equality, inclusion, economic fairness, addressing violence and promoting women’s political participation.

A variation on the subject of support to the feminist policy ecosystem can be found in grants to projects producing evidence and analysis and calling for change around certain issues underpinning gender inequality and women’s human rights. Examples include:

- support to Fawcett Society, Women’s Budget Group in the UK on impact of austerity cuts and gender pay gap on poverty and inequality that hit women hard;
- support to Asylum Aid; legal support for women asylum seekers and their children detained at Yarl’s Wood Immigration Removal Centre, and research into their living conditions and processing;
- abortion rights and access to reproductive health services in the UK, Argentina, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Poland, and Trinidad and Tobago, as well as practical and social support to women from Ireland coming to the UK to access abortion services.

What is certain is that today, as the FRT winds down its operations, even the stronger, more established organisations in the UK are in a deep funding crisis in the face of increasing and overwhelming need. The Women’s Therapy centre is testimony to the change and erosion of the feminist fabric. New organisations emerge, but there is also a sense of regret at the loss of former leading and valued outfits such as the Women’s Therapy Centre, which was a pioneer in making therapy accessible and affordable to women who could not otherwise access it. FRT funded the Centre in 2015 with £12,000 to support core costs to help keep it open. It closed in 2019.

An interesting example of bridge funding is the award in 2010 to the Arbour Young BME Women’s Social Inclusion Project in Tower Hamlets. This project ‘provided a safe environment for newly arrived women with no recourse to public funds to receive accredited English language and life skills across Tower Hamlets’ (Award Report). The FRT grant of £3,000 allowed Arbour to maintain activities and pay salaries when one stream of funding was terminated and the next delayed for seven months. According to the grantee, this FRT bridging support ‘ensured the ongoing delivery of the project to vulnerable women already

enrolled on the course, and ensured valuable knowledge, expertise and relationships with service users and partner organisations were not lost' (Award Report).

Intersectionality

In many projects (and reflected also in the minutes of Board meetings) there is an explicit commitment to a goal of intersectionality in funding feminist change. Intersectionality refers to the interplay of gender identities, age, race, class and sexuality and has been a driver and challenge for movement building during various waves of feminist change. Most of the projects funded by FRT reflect inclusive principles of intersectionality in approach, identify vulnerable women/girls who will benefit from the funding, or specifically award funding to projects supporting LGBTQI communities and initiatives. For example, one of the final awards listed in the database, in January 2021, is for Unikuir LGBTI+ in Ankara, Turkey, funding workshops aimed at increasing the capacities of people working in civil society organisations to pursue intersectional approaches to feminism. Refugee women and women with disabilities were also encouraged to come to these workshops. Another example is the core support to the Lesbian Immigration Support Group in Manchester in 2011.

Other examples include a course on intersectionality with varied feminist activists in Athens to support coalition building (2019), and an online platform for gender equality and disability on intersectional understanding of sexual and reproductive rights in Argentina (2017). In the Kyrgyz Republic in 2013, the Bishkek Feminist Collective received funding for the Open School Project, which 'will provide space for women, lesbians, gays, bisexuals, transsexuals, ethnic minorities, youth, and other disadvantaged people to learn from each other by emancipatory educational process through both formal classes and ready access to a curated library' (FRT Website).

It is good practice, not seen often enough, to fund a selection of projects dedicated to women with disability and addressing how their inclusion in services and actions is considered. They are not just an add-on but are at the centre of the projects funded. These include a training programme for women and girls with disabilities in Bangladesh, addressing women's rights and the rights of persons with disabilities, and aiming to shape localised advocacy actions on access to, and inclusion in, government services.

Another focus of intersectionality is the funding directed specifically to projects by Black feminists and women of colour – women who have experienced racial inequality and injustice. Examples here include:

- Trafford Black and Minority Ethnic Women's Service – a convention on intersectionality between Black feminist theory, activism, and experience of survivors;

- young BME Women’s Inclusion Project in Tower Hamlets (the Arbour Project, see above, p. 24), enabling newly arrived women to acquire accredited English language skills and support with integration;
- documentary making, updating the film *A Place of Rage* documenting the achievements of African American women in the context of civil rights, Black power, lesbian and gay rights, and the feminist movement;
- support to NAZ (sexual health agency in London) on research on BME and LGB intersections and awareness.

Given its origins in the *Feminist Review* Collective and journal, it is perhaps not surprising that academic women, researchers and writers were a notable group receiving grants from the Trust. The review found 18 projects where academics were funded to workshop, attend conferences, or publish and disseminate research findings. More broadly, other projects that were funded involved academic women in some way, either through board memberships, networks, or related activism beyond their core academic work.

This theme continues into grants that supported leadership and career support for, and by, women. Examples include:

- Global South Feminist Writing Workshop;
- Women’s Budget Group, creating networks of early career feminist economists;
- supporting activists and PhD students to attend the British Sociological Association Gender Study Group conference;
- leadership training to women from diverse backgrounds in the UK voluntary sector;
- women’s leadership workshop in Argentina to identify good practices, obstacles, and training needs of community leaders.

Coalitions of joint action as a form of movement building are found in a number of projects supported by the Trust. These brought together different actors such as service providers, activists, academics, artists and workers, to effect change in ways that went beyond simple target groups. For example, in 2013, the FRT funded the Women’s Resource Centre in London to help set up The London Violence Against Women and Girls Consortium. This comprised 22 existing organisations in a feminist, anti-racist coalition to improve cooperation and access to resources.

The WRC hope this work will pose a viable feminist alternative to competitive tendering and could be one of the key factors in determining the continued survival of a diverse women’s sector. (FRT Website)

A common trend was the demand to respond to the impact of austerity in the UK on the cuts to public services. This emphasis was notable in support to survivors of domestic violence, e.g. training of a peer support network for Tyneside Women’s Health, and leaflets and

information for Women's Aid Orkney. Support and commitment to advocating and securing human rights is a common thread across most of the projects funded by the Trust, involving support to women coming together and organising together to campaign, support or educate on rights or social change. Women-led organisations predominate in the list of grantees.

There are examples of funding being leveraged from other sources as a result of FRT funding. The interviews with grantees highlight this leveraging role of FRT, including the Justice for Magdalenes case study on p. 20 – 21. One of the Trustees emphasises:

This leveraging took a number of forms. Firstly, there were quite a few occasions where we offered funding contingent on the group obtaining a certain percentage of funding from another source. I worked closely with the groups to support them on this and in all but one occasion they were successful. There was the leverage where we gave awards to support fundraising and then there were the awards where we believed that by giving an initial award to get a project underway, we hopefully added a status to the project and so attracted other funders.

She gives the example of a project supporting Syrian refugee women and girls in Edinburgh, which provided Arabic language support to enable women to access frontline services. An award of £6,000 was made, to be matched with funding coming from another supporter of the project.

In the document review, Dr Teresa Cairns, the researcher leading the Mass Observation Directive project (2008) on experiences of menopause and mid-life by women and men, reported that the project had received a matching grant from the British Academy as a result of FRT funding. It is interesting to note how pioneering this approach was, long pre-dating the current focus on health services, attitudes and information regarding menopause and gynaecology.

Another contribution of the FRT to movement building was its support to the celebrations of feminist organisations, e.g. the 2014 Kate Millett conference and debates on second-wave feminism the 30th and 40th anniversary celebrations of Southall Black Sisters, and the 35th anniversary of the Rights of Women legal advice organisation. Funding of feminist gatherings, conferences and participation of disadvantaged women/groups in conferences and discussions is another discernible type of movement building support given by the Trust.

A common refrain in various award reports from grassroots organisations in the UK over the years is that of women's organisations being under threat from funding cuts, uncertain funding and changes in policy at local and national level affecting funding of services and activities. That this remains as true in 2023 does invite frustration and reflection. There are initiatives out there amongst organisations and some funders do highlight this issue. However, the constant threat to funding for vulnerable groups, adversely affecting women, raises an issue for funders like FRT who have relatively small amounts to distribute.

According to Trustees, much debate took place over the years about funding direct services that should be provided by the state/government. It was felt that FRT could not plug all the gaps and that, for impact and suitability, this funding must continue to seek out feminist-inspired projects aimed at supporting collaboration for change across a range of issues and types of projects, rather than trying to staunch the wound of inadequate delivery of core services that were being cut by national and local decision-makers and budget-holders. This did not mean that FRT did not seek to support advocacy and pressure on the economic and social impact of cuts. Its support to the Fawcett Society, the Women's Budget Group, the Centre for Women and Democracy and Homeworkers Worldwide (Women working in the North network) over 2009–2011 is notable in this regard, driving research, advocacy and campaigns.

5. *The New Landscape of Feminist Funding*

We are witnessing the apparent rise of new feminist funds at different levels, which in theory and principle are committed to grassroots funding as part of what they do. These include:

- (1) Global and multilateral funds managed through international organisations and funded mainly by states (statutory and aid funding) with partnerships and support from private philanthropy in some cases. Examples are:
 - the *UN Fund for Gender Equality*, established in 2009 'to support national, women-led civil society organizations in achieving women's economic and political empowerment and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)'.⁷ It has awarded grants of USD65 million to 121 projects in 80 countries.
 - *UN Trust Fund to End Violence against Women*, which has existed since 1996 and has provided USD215 million to 646 initiatives across 140 countries and territories. Some 62.4% of recipients are women's rights organisations.⁷

- (2) Private philanthropic foundations: these foundations are well known to feminist activists and women's organisations seeking support either directly or through larger intermediaries funded by them. Here are some examples:
 - *Oak Foundation*, located in Geneva, was established in 1983 and now has seven global programmes and four country programmes. In 2022 it made grants totalling USD481.62 million. One of its main programmes is the *Issues Affecting Women Programme*, which has a very explicit feminist and movement-building focus with the

⁷ <https://www.unwomen.org/en/trust-funds/un-trust-fund-to-end-violence-against-women>

tagline of ‘supporting vibrant movements led by women that are transforming lives and communities’.⁸ It sets out an agenda for making these changes at different levels:

Support women-led rights-based services that address violence against women; provide primarily long-term support as an act of solidarity, helping movements to achieve the lasting change needed for us all to thrive; and connect organisations and movements, and resource them to learn from each other and work together, to develop knowledge and skills, and to plan, organise, and mobilise.

What distinguishes Oak as a funder is its commitment to ‘engage with other donors and philanthropic actors to leverage more and better funding to advance women’s rights around the world’. In 2022 it made 22 grants, both country-specific and international, amounting to USD33.32 million. Oak provides both project and core funding, with an increasing focus on the latter, which now constitutes 42% of its overall grant making.

- The *Sigrid Rausing Trust*, based in London, was established in 1995 and is a well-known funder of human rights including feminist activists and organisations through its two programmes on women’s rights (52 current grantees and 86 past grantees) and on LGBTI rights (28 current grantees and 22 past grantees).⁹ It has a reputation for being a flexible funder in terms of funding an organisation based on its strategy and work rather than on specific projects. It also provides partnership grants with a duration of one year which can be extended to a cycle of three years’ unrestricted funding. Grantees are identified by recommendations and the Trust’s own fieldwork. It is therefore not possible to apply without being invited to do so. The grantees include a range of grassroots organisations from various regions (with a strong focus on Central and Eastern Europe and Eurasia), as well as established larger women’s rights organisations that partner with grassroots groups. In 2021 the Trust’s women’s rights programme was its largest allocation of grants, at GBP7 million, with the LGBTI programme at GBP2 million.
- The *Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation*, based in Seattle, has emerged as a key player in gender equality funding globally. This is affirmed by an ambitious strategy, launched in March 2018, focusing on economic empowerment for women and girls through financial and market inclusion and the support of self-help groups led by women, with funding of USD170 million over four years. In 2020 the Foundation established a dedicated Division on Gender Equality to reflect work across its various challenges and programmes and to integrate gender equality more fully. In 2021, Melinda French

⁸ <https://oakfnd.org/programmes/issues-affecting-women/>

⁹ <https://www.sigrid-rausing-trust.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/SRT-Annual-Report-2021-PRINT-AW.pdf> ; <https://www.sigrid-rausing-trust.org/what-we-do/>

Gates announced a five-year, USD650-million investment to further the economic empowerment of women. This is focused on ‘cash, care, and data’ as the entry points, drawing on strategic partnership with the Centre for Global Development.¹⁰ The grants are channelled in the main through international agencies, international NGOs, universities and established institutional partners in the global South.

(3) Large charitable foundations, such as:

- The *Global Fund for Women*, a non-profit grant-making foundation founded in 1986 by four women challenging the gaps in funding to women’s human rights. Over 32 years it has funded USD184.7 million to over 5,200 organisations in 176 countries. It is regarded as a leading feminist funder; its income comprises a range of individual giving, other foundations, governments and multilateral organisations, corporations, and investments. It describes itself as ‘a feminist fund with an intersectional lens’ and aim to provide general operating support grants – unrestricted, flexible money, to cover the real costs of social justice work¹¹.
- *Kvinna til Kvinna [Woman to Woman] Foundation*, a Swedish feminist foundation established in 1993 out of the women and peace movements in response to the mass rapes of the Yugoslav wars. It works with 100 partner organisations in 20 countries defending women’s rights, gender equality and justice, and pursuing feminist peace. In 2022 it allocated SEK192.7 million (GBP14.8 million / USD18.4 million) to 140 women’s rights organisations in sub-Saharan Africa, the Middle East and North Africa, the South Caucasus and Europe. It receives the bulk of its funding (78%) from Swedish International Development Cooperation (SIDA).¹²

(4) NGO-led, grassroots-driven funds by feminist organisations such as MADRE, WILPF and FRIDA:

- *FRIDA* (Flexibility, Resources, Inclusivity, Action) is a youth-led young feminist fund founded in 2008, which has grown over the period 2015–2021 through learning from, and further developing, its feminist participatory grant-making practice. It is refining its funding of movement building aimed at a new generation of feminist collectives. FRIDA provides multiyear, flexible core grants to young and emerging feminist groups run by young women, girls, and trans and intersex youth. During 2021, it made 1,296 grants totalling USD2.79 million.

¹⁰ <https://www.gatesfoundation.org/our-work/programs/gender-equality>

¹¹ <https://www.globalfundforwomen.org/what-we-do/our-approach/>

¹² See Annual Report for 2022, p.44. <https://kvinnaatillkvinna.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/The-Kvinna-till-Kvinna-Foundation-annual-report-2022.pdf>. The reliance on government funding suggests Kvinna til Kvinna is close to being a version of the state-funded women’s funds discussed below.

FRIDA provides young feminist organizers with the resources they need to amplify their voices and bring attention to the social justice issues they care about. We enable the support, flexibility and networks to sustain young feminist visions.¹³

FRIDA received funding from a range of sources including the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, Sigrid Rausing Trust, Oak Foundation, Ford Foundation and the government of Sweden.

- *MADRE* has been a leading supporter of community-based women’s organisations since 1986, through grant making, organisational strengthening and legal advocacy. It focuses on themes of gender violence, climate justice, just peace and campaigns. Over 35 years it has allocated USD52 million in grants and in-kind contributions.¹⁴ The types of organisation with which *MADRE* partners provide services such as shelters for survivors of violence, health clinics and water conservation, among others. It funds movement building to strengthen advocacy for policy and legal changes, supports human rights defenders, and helps develop leadership and skills. Its partners and projects are located in Nicaragua, Guatemala, Haiti, Colombia, Kenya, Palestine, Syria, Sudan and Iraq.

We fund local organizations, networks and groups that are ‘under the radar’ of other international funders and large aid organizations. We focus our partnerships on women-led organizations that prioritize the leadership of young women and girls, Indigenous women, Afro-descendant women, LGBTIQ people and people with disabilities.

- *WILPF* (Women’s International League for Peace and Freedom) is the longest-established pacifist and feminist organisation in the world, and is based in Geneva. Dating back to 1915, it focuses its work on anti-militarism, movement building and feminist peace and security. *WILPF* engaged in direct grant making to women’s groups and feminist allies in Syria over 2018–2022, through the Feminist Movement for Change project. This involved making grants of CHF5000 (GBP4,400 / USD5,580) to unregistered, grassroots groups, and grants of CHF25,000 (GBP22,340 / USD27,900) to established groups. *WILPF* developed and uses a Holistic Feminist Resourcing Approach, and its grants include flexible funding, technical support and networking opportunities. Funding for the Syria project came from the UK government (Foreign Commonwealth and Development Office) and the Oak Foundation. A review conducted in 2022 found:

¹³ <https://youngfeministfund.org>; <https://youngfeministfund.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/FRIDA-2022-Annual-Report.pdf>; <https://youngfeministfund.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/FRIDA-RE-SOURCING-CONNECTIONS-interactive.pdf>

¹⁴ <https://www.madre.org>

WILPF sought to free Syrian feminist leaders from some of the constant pressure of meeting basic costs, allowing them the time and resources they need to think and act strategically, focus on their organisational needs, and further their feminist agendas. In other words, by adopting flexible core funding instead of project-based and top-down funding policies driven by donor needs and interests, resources can be allocated where they are most needed as identified by each organisation's leaders and staff.¹⁵

FRT Trustees highlight other feminist funds they consider to be doing feminist work to transform power relationships and support diverse grassroots movement building and projects. These include:¹⁶

- Mama Cash in The Netherlands, grant making and accompaniment to movement building with women's, girl's, trans and intersex people's movements globally;
- The Astraea Lesbian Foundation for Justice, with its tagline of 'Hyperlocal Impact. Global Reach', supporting LGBTQI human rights and activists in the US and internationally;
- Urgent Action Fund for Feminist Activism, providing rapid response funding to women and to trans and non-binary activists. There are also now four Urgent Action Sister Funds covering different regions and global locations.

(5) National level, statutory funds in countries with consciously feminist foreign policy frameworks

Sweden was the first country to adopt an official 'feminist foreign policy' in 2014, fronted by the energetic leadership of Margot Wallström. This was an important cultural and resource shift and made waves. By 2022, a group of ten countries including Canada, Mexico, Germany, and Chile, had adopted the label and committed to taking action to support feminist organising and change.

It is evident how instrumental Sweden became in the funding ecosystem of international feminism, funding a range of organisations at international and local levels. This influence can be found in increased funds for women's organisations and feminist action internationally, including UN agencies, feminist NGOs (including most of those mentioned in this section), as well as funding channelled through Swedish bilateral aid directly to programmes and organisations in the global South. Its list of thematic entry points and priorities reads like a familiar catalogue of issues: human rights, freedom from violence, participation in peace

¹⁵ <https://www.wilpf.org/publications/side-by-side-on-the-journey-to-feminist-peace-applying-wilpfs-holistic-feminist-resourcing-approach-in-syria/> p.6.

¹⁶ <https://www.mamacash.org/en/en-homepage;>
[https://www.mamacash.org/media/230714_mc_ar_4pager_eng_digital.pdf;](https://www.mamacash.org/media/230714_mc_ar_4pager_eng_digital.pdf)
[https://www.astraeafoundation.org;](https://www.astraeafoundation.org) [https://urgentactionfund.org;](https://urgentactionfund.org) [https://urgentactionfund.org/sister-funds/.](https://urgentactionfund.org/sister-funds/)

efforts, political participation, economic empowerment and sexual and reproductive health and rights.

A second exemplar of a feminist approach is emerging from Canada, in particular with its self-declared 'feminist international assistance policy' launched in June 2017. New funding mechanisms were also launched by Global Affairs Canada, including the Women's Voice and Leadership Program with funding of CAD150 million over five years for women's rights organisations in the global South.¹⁷ The focus is on flexible funding for local women's organisations to give direct support to the empowerment and rights of girls or women, including through capacity development and networks. Funding targets for gender equality have also been set for bilateral and multilateral aid. In 2019, the government announced an Equality Fund that would receive the full CAD300 million contribution to support global feminist movements. The Equality Fund grew out of feminist partnering and funding initiatives dating back to 1976 in the forms of The Match International Centre and, since 2013, The Match International Fund. It works with a blend of grant making, investment and philanthropy, guided by 'principles for feminist funding'.¹⁸

There have been some criticisms of feminist foreign policy from activists who argue that the systemic changes of power and resources do not go far enough in terms of challenging other areas of government policy, for example trade or militarism.

We also know that while recent government commitments might be big, they pale in comparison with spending that compounds inequality for women, girls and LGBT people, such as increasing militarisation, growth based on natural resources, and an unjust economic system.¹⁹

Yet traditionalists also complain that the feminist foreign policy creates diplomatic tensions precisely because it questions these areas and prioritises women's rights and gender equality.

A recent change of government in October 2022, indicating a rightward shift in Swedish politics, has seen a deliberate ending of its feminist foreign policy, with implications for feminist funds and activists. It begs the question how feminist approaches can achieve traction on sustainability in state-led policy spaces. A group of feminist activists reacting to the Swedish government's decision to drop its feminist foreign policy underscores what it means:

... first and foremost, Sweden's decision to call its foreign policy feminist gave hope and inspiration to feminist activists around the world. Women human rights defenders knew they had an ally on the global stage. This solidarity is vital as attacks on feminist activists and LGBTQIA+ people increase ... Sweden's feminist foreign policy

¹⁷ <https://www.devex.com/news/canada-s-new-foreign-aid-policy-puts-focus-on-women-rights-90458>

¹⁸ <https://equalityfund.ca/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/Feminist-Philanthropy-EN.pdf>

¹⁹ <https://www.theguardian.com/global-development/2019/jul/02/gender-equality-support-1bn-boost-how-to-spend-it>

made it clear, once and for all, that gender equality was not a side issue. Rather, it is central when looking at global security, economic prosperity and climate disaster.²⁰

In Conclusion

In considering this landscape of feminist funding, the question is whether these funders can and will reach the varied, modest, and often shoestring-budgeted groups, activities and mobilisers that the Feminist Review Trust often reached.

It is interesting to note the interconnections and interdependence amongst the different types of feminist funds outlined here. Smaller, radical funds often rely on funds from larger funds and established foundations as well as from governments, while often also having a strategy for obtaining individual or public donations. This interdependence underscores the opportunities and constraints of replicating a feminist funding model that can reach and work with grassroots groups, actions, and events.

The funds outlined above are professionalised in the sense of having paid professionals managing and distributing funds; they also vary in size but are much larger than FRT in terms of income for grant making. With greater professionalisation, projectisation, overheads, systems of tracking and learning, it may indeed be small community-inspired initiatives of the kind FRT funded that lose out in the marketplace of funding women's rights and feminist change. Not all funding needs and groups are media-friendly, high-profile, or identified with dynamic individual changemakers.

When discussing feminist funds, one must distinguish the extent to which a funder is simply a fund manager with processes and staffing to follow the grants, from that to which they are driven by values and practices committed to transformative change. Many funders state, for example, that they exist to improve certain situations, secure rights, or tackle underlying causes of inequality or injustice, but may be more limited as regards a feminist focus and lens on transforming the lives of women and girls, together with a commitment to intersectional and inclusive approaches.

One Trustee suggested that the power of the Feminist Review Trust lay in its existence outside the 'charitable industrial complex', and that collective ways of working were precisely why it could do what it did. But this may explain why it might not have survived contact with a more 'professionalised' approach that sought to replicate the structures or practices of philanthropic foundations or large NGOs. It is not fully clear how one could replicate a non-remunerated, collective model of funding by women for women, grounded in feminist movement building today and into the future.

²⁰ <https://msmagazine.com/2023/01/19/sweden-feminist-foreign-policy/>

Another of the FRT Trustees reflected that ‘insofar as we did any good, they [other feminist funders] won’t do the good that we did’. This perhaps speaks to women’s organising and networks that grew like the FRT itself and also faced challenges in sustaining the ecosystem of feminist action and funding. Existing and new funds, in their own times, will face the challenge to reach women where they are in ways that can allow fledgling projects to be funded and to bring direct benefit, as well as having potential to achieve greater reach and greater impact on the underlying drivers of change around women’s rights, justice, economic fairness, ending violence against women, intersectional and inclusive organising, and celebrating feminist culture and arts.

This fragility of feminist funding endures and is not new – it was what inspired the setting up of the Feminist Review Trust over 20 years ago. Interviews with Trustees and grantees confirm a set of trends in feminist organising and funding to the ‘women’s sector’ that reflect a situation of constant needs for fundraising, seeking volunteers to keep things going, facing the threat of closure and the pressures this brings, and constant self-reinvention so as to be seen as ‘innovative’ when seeking support for services, events, or campaigns.

The constraints and adverse factors operating upon small feminist funders such as the FRT include (but are not limited to):

- confusion and questioning by funding bodies about supporting organisations and projects aimed at women and girls or single-sex services in the context of media and political debates and controversies;
- a long history of threadbare, uncertain, and insecure financing for statutory responsibilities in areas around violence against women, immigration and legal aid, with the pressures falling on civil society and non-governmental organisations to step in;
- the long-term implications in the UK of austerity policies affecting core public services and social welfare since 2010, which have negatively impacted on poverty, violence, education, health, and many other areas of life, placing a particularly heavy burden on women;
- in recent years, the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on networking and relationship building amongst feminist/women’s organisations and with funders, despite the gains in benefits in terms of reach and access afforded by online communications platforms.

Organisations have coalesced to document, publicise, and lobby on the risks to funding and the impact of economic policies on women, and indeed the FRT has funded some of this work. For example, see the 2018 report, *Life-Changing and Life-Saving: Funding for the women’s sector*, by the Women’s Budget Group and the Women’s Resource Centre.²¹

²¹ <https://wbg.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/12/WBG-Funding-Report-2.pdf>

In the UK, in terms of non-statutory funding, organisations seek funds from a similar pool of philanthropic funds.²² Some organisations or initiatives funded by FRT have received or sought funding from the same, shrinking pool of Trusts. These include ROSA, Smallwood Trust and Esmée Fairbairn Foundation, which have specifically feminist or women-centred mission statements. Some of the grantees also refer to the larger, multi-mandate funds, Comic Relief and the National Lottery. These offer direct public funding for various projects and organisations but not necessarily or exclusively through a feminist, gender equality, or activist funding lens. Grantees also benefit from long-standing social justice funders such as the Joseph Rowntree Charitable Trust.

Another, analogous source for funding for women affected by economic, social and legal hardship and discrimination is through community foundations that serve local communities. The growth of such foundations is notable as a focus for many local initiatives – ‘a place-based approach ... to leverage local philanthropy to address local problems’²³. While some of them support the activities of women’s groups or activities and services that target women in communities, they do not necessarily have the feminist or activist analysis of social, economic and political change that informs many of the projects and groups funded by the FRT.

What is clear, globally and in the UK, is that the need for funding and support to women’s rights and women’s organisations remains; there is still a deep well of ‘hard-to-fund’ grassroots projects and initiatives. It is currently estimated that ‘less than 1% of gender equality funding actually reaches grassroots organisations’, according to recent research and briefings by ODI (Overseas Development Institute) and AWID (Association for Women’s Rights in Development):²⁴

2021 research by AWID found women’s rights organizations receive only 0.13% of total Official Development Assistance (ODA), staggeringly 0.4% of all gender-related aid, and only 0.42% of foundation grants are allocated towards women’s rights. AWID also found 48% of women’s rights and feminist organizations from the Global South seeking funding report their most recent fiscal year budget was less than USD 30,000.

This fragility of funding is a challenge for all concerned and something that requires collaboration with a range of actors to fight for change and bring more recognition and security to the core work, values and rights of feminist action, work and organisations.

²² <https://rosauk.org>; <https://www.smallwoodtrust.org.uk>; <https://www.jrct.org.uk>; <https://esmeefairbairn.org.uk>

²³ <https://www.ukcommunityfoundations.org/about-us>

²⁴ AWID (2021b) ‘Where is the money for feminist organizing? Data snapshots and a call to action’, AWID Brief https://www.awid.org/sites/default/files/2022-01/AWID_Research_WITM_Brief_ENG.pdf; Emilie Tant and Diana Jiménez Thomas Rodríguez, ‘How to partner with feminist movements for transformative change’, ODI Policy brief. London: ODI, 2022; https://cdn.odi.org/media/documents/ODI_Policybrief_How_to_partner_with_feminist_movements_300622.pdf.

The challenge to feminist funding is how to build and sustain change, whether through projects, movement building or campaigns. The key seems to lie in acquiring the know-how to link up individual, group and systemic levels of change. This requires collaboration, critical learning from practice, and an appetite for taking risks and being committed to long-term impact.

The emergence and spread of new movements such as #MeToo and elements of the movements around climate change indicate that the desire and action for solidarity and non-institutionalised responses to social change remain. New types of people-to-people activism and funding are emerging from movements and protests, global online collaborations facilitated by social media and crowdfunding for projects. Also, the rise of social cohesion and community projects coming out of the response to greater inequalities and poverty in the UK through food banks or local fundraising efforts for women's groups indicate a willingness to mobilise even in challenging times.

It is important to reiterate that the FRT's key distinguishing feature is it is as an activist-led and activist-managed trust with no paid staff or fundraising arm. It is this type of organisation that may prove difficult to repeat or replicate. Its funding pot of £500,000 over 20 years does not match the resources of other funds. We cannot compare apples and oranges, of course, but the FRT's story highlights what is possible with small amounts of money in terms of reach, scope, and diversity of impact. The database of FRT award holders is testimony to this possibility and to the continuing, overwhelming need for such small funds for grassroots, small initiatives that do not require large amounts of money to support their activism and work in their communities. Many such initiatives would not be eligible or able to apply to many of the mainstream, established funds and would potentially rely on intermediaries to take on their projects and initiatives and change how they work to create change.

Grant making is not only about value for money, sustainability, or even results, although these hallmarks of contemporary monitoring, evaluation and learning are important in terms of accountability for monies spent and measuring the intended change and impact effected by the funding. However, when deployed in a rigid, 'textbook' manner, such quantitative indicators merely provide an overview of action and an accounting of labour by the funder and the grantees. What can be lost or missed is the creative, organic change processes that a relatively small fund, run by a group of dedicated activists, can achieve when reaching out and deliberately funding grassroots events, programmes, initiatives and groups that would not necessarily come under the purview of a fully professionalised fund.

What is true is that such activist labour may no longer be possible or accessible in the current economy of the UK and the wider world. Yet there are lessons to be learned from the workings and history of the FRT that may warn against possible over-professionalisation of feminist funding; it risks missing the grassroots reach, risk taking and movement building that funders aspire to help create. What is sometimes missing is the intangible quality of 'activism' and

‘activist funding’ that has its roots in the collective and feminist origins of the *Feminist Review* journal and, later, the Trust.

The transforming and changing future of these organisations is occurring alongside a vibrant, inclusive, challenging rise of new organic movements and initiatives, driven by a younger generation of activists. We see a passing of the baton as the intergenerational change navigates a world facing many challenges of economy and poverty, peace and security, environment and the climate crisis, social change, equality and justice. The struggle does indeed go on, and the need for grassroots funding for feminist approaches, organising and action has never been more important or necessary if we are to grow these many new shoots and shore up the hard-won gains of earlier generations of feminist activists and women’s organisations.

6. Legacy of the Feminist Review Trust

The FRT defies all categorisations. It is easier to start by saying what the FRT is not.

- It is not an NGO with paid professional staff.
- It is not a private philanthropy foundation with endowed, investment, or private family funding.
- It is not a state-supported organisation distributing aid or welfare funds.
- It is not a local welfare association run by well-intentioned women in civil society.

Rather, FRT is a dynamic activist-powered collective of feminists that grew from the *Feminist Review* to create and drive a grant-making organism, funding hard-to-fund grassroots projects that were driving feminist action and change across the UK and globally.

The resources came from an incredibly rare and innovative profit-sharing publishing deal negotiated by the women of the *Feminist Review* Collective with the academic publisher of the *Feminist Review*, an academic journal. Many members share roots in academic research and roles; others come from legal, financial and third-sector professional backgrounds and identify as socialist and socialist-inspired in terms of the collective culture of the Trust. The Board is made up of ten members at this time.

This is the size of the outfit, the collective, the woman power, that many grantees and observers often assume to be a significant, well-staffed and funded office. It is this Feminist Review Trust engine that

- negotiated and acquired its ongoing financial resources through a notable publishing deal;
- navigated the registration and recognition of the new Trust by the Charity Commission, with a change of rules;

- contributed the hours, days and weekends of labour to shape the governance, management and functioning of the Trust in a professional and accountable manner;
- dedicated their skills and time to reading every single application and widening the Trust's reach through networks and online invitations hosted through a website and simple application process;
- became both a funder of last resort and an enabler of first steps for hundreds of individuals, groups, communities, campaigns, services, and human rights defenders working at grassroots level to change and improve the lives of women and girls, both in the UK and across the world.

This review draws lessons from the scope, processes, values and projects supported and promoted by the Trust over 20 years. It is not merely nostalgic, it aims to ensure that the instincts to support feminist causes, coalitions and change are captured and recorded for the future. It is an opportunity to learn from the struggles and responsibilities of establishing and running a feminist funding trust.

The need and demand for such funding has not abated, and there is merit in not losing time reinventing efforts that already can provide insights. This review demonstrates the need and demand for small grassroots funding and the possibilities and assets for change it can affect. It shows how much a collaborative approach with activist labour can achieve and indicates where new sources of grassroots feminist funding can emerge in the future while bridging and building understanding and solidarity with a new generation of activists and activism.

ANNEX 1 -- Projects Reviewed

(1) PROJECTS REVIEWED

An overview of 177 project summaries from the FRT website database up to January 2021. These were reviewed and categorised according to the following themes:

Violence against Women & Girls	36 projects funded
Arts & Culture	28 projects funded
Migrant & Refugee Women	27 projects funded
Running Feminist Groups/Centres	18 projects funded
Health-focused Projects	17 projects funded
Abortion and Sexual & Reproductive Rights	15 projects funded
Memory, Narratives, & Oral Histories	13 projects funded
Women with Disabilities	9 projects funded
Economy & Work	8 projects funded
Education-focused Projects	7 projects funded
Justice Processes & Systems	7 projects funded
Journalism & Media	7 projects funded
Peace & Conflict	6 projects funded
Sex Workers	6 projects funded
Environment & Climate Change	3 projects funded

(2) FULLER PROJECT DOCUMENTS RECEIVED FROM FRT FOR REVIEW (48 Projects)

*Indicates that the project is also a featured case study in the FRT history project

Year	Project Name	Award (£)	Documents available
2005	The Lilith Project – to support a seminar training day for hostels and housing providers on the needs of women who have survived violence	£1,000	Award Report
2005	Dr Jodi Mellor	£1,000	Booklet produced on higher education for South Asian community
2005	Eskalera Karakole – Madrid – feminist social centre – support for new audio visual centre	£1,000	Update letter from grantee
2005	Ladyfest Brighton – festival workshops, discussion	£1,000	Festival Programme
2005	FEM 05 – national conference on women’s rights – Sheffield University	£1,000	Conference Report; expenditure of grant; feedback from attendees
2006	Leeds, Gender Study Group of British Sociological Association (BSA) – postgrad conference	£300	Award Report
2006	Andrea Dworkin commemorative conference	N/A	Award Report. Grant is not on website database
2006	Action research to improve practice of fast-track process for women detainees at Yarl’s Wood Immigration Removal Centre*	£1,420	Award Report; account of expenditures
2006	Project in Botswana – workshop on knowledge management in organisations		Not on website database; slides, receipts, attendance sheet; expenditure accounts – not in GBP
2007	UK Abortion Rights Campaign 40th anniversary *	£ 5,000	Award report; account of expenditures
2007	Rape Crisis Scotland – oral history project	£1,000	Award Report (states £1500 was received)
2007	Respect my Choice campaign – Trinidad and Tobago*	£2,000	Award Report and expenditures
2007	English language classes with sex workers in London	£1,500	Report of 2007 explains delays and setbacks; email by May to say classes had started

2008	Israel/Palestine -- 'Women and Their Bodies', abortion and reproductive health rights*	£2,000	Award Report
2008	Asylum Aid – promoting Charter of Rights of Women seeking asylum	£4,000	Award report, including indicators of success; account of expenditures
2008	Leadership skills for women in voluntary sector	£4,500	Award Report; list of attendees (20 women)
2008	Feminist Art Studio – Tbilisi, Georgia. 10 women artists have space; 2 public discussion events, library resources, affordable materials	£5,000	Award Report & detailed financial report
2008	Rights of Women – free dissemination of legal guides to many social areas and VAW; free places at conference for BME and refugee women	£5,000	Award Report and order forms with FRT fully acknowledged for support; good data on reach & impact
2008	Dr Teresa Cairns – Mass Observation Directive for Research on Menopause with women and men	£5,000	Award Report. Received matched funding from British Academy; rich report and findings
2009	Transnational Feminisms Conference – Manchester	£500	Award Report – travel bursaries, participation of women asylum seekers, conference packs
2009	Fawcett Society – core funding in run-up to 2010 general election	£2,000	Award Report, letter
2009	Southall Black Sisters – 30th anniversary networking and celebratory event	£4,000	Award Report and receipts
2010	Arbour – Young BME Women's Social Inclusion Project – Tower Hamlets – bridge funding	£3,000	Award Report
2010	Rights of Women – 35th anniversary Conference on violence against women	£1,500	Award Report – funded participation of smaller grassroots groups across UK
2011	Homeworkers Worldwide (Women Working in the North network)	£2,000	No funding reports available. Action Research Summary report
2011	Women in Prison, 'State of the Estate: Report on the women's custodial estate 2011–12'	£2000	Extracts from report
2011	Irish Magdalenes in the UK: A Restorative Justice Project	£7,287	No reports provided; interview with grantee for follow-up change
2011	Fawcett Society – core funding	£9,811	Award Report

2013	Digital Desperados – Glasgow*	£4,000	Award Report; invoice; photos
2016	Breastfeeding in Leicester – Leicester Mammals - Community breastfeeding peer support programme involving women from neighbourhoods with high levels of inequality *	£2,796	Award Report; Budget
2016	Afghan Women newly arrived in the UK – ACAA Afghan and Central Asian Association	£3, 376	Award report; expenses; workshops
2017	Violence against socially excluded women in Ghana	£1,500	Award Report; Budget; receipts. International Federation of Women Lawyers in Ghana
2017	Campaigning against violence against women – Bosnia and Herzegovina	£2,000	Centre for Legal Assistance of Women; good records, detailed accounts. Self-defence booklet, city protests
2018	Addressing anti-choice threat in Poland – Gals4Gals *	£8,000	Application form, Award Report; Budget; photos - Polish pro-choice campaign billboards
2018	Women’s Budget Group – network of early career economists	£7,002	Application Form, Award Report. Early Career Women’s Economist Network
2018	Digital Feminist Programme in Peru*	£ 8,000	Application Form; Award acceptance form, Award Report
2019	Southall Black Sisters	£ 4,000	No reports – for celebration of 40th anniversary; had also supported 30th
2019)	<i>Roshni Tariqiyati Tanzeem</i> – Sindh (Pakistan) – feminist action on industrial & agricultural environmental pollution – building groups, awareness, targeting women and men	£10,000	Award acceptance form; Award Report (01092021), expenses. Emailed for interview. Very flood-affected and disrupted but working on the activities and supporting participants on crisis-related issues
2020	Women’s Aid Orkney, Scotland	£2,225	Award Report (09092022); Excel Budget - £2,578.50; output leaflets. Updating leaflets for services
2020	Books For Libraries in Zimbabwe – Weaver Press	£3,990	Application Form.

			Placing books by and about women in Zimbabwe in academic and public libraries
2020	Ruta Pacífica de las Mujeres - Peace Radio – Colombia*	£6,080	Application form. Created 48 episodes of weekly programme, dissemination to other outlets, training of 10 women to be reporters and producers
2020	Sister System – Tottenham, London	£4,992	Application Form; Award Report (Jan 2022); photos. Peer-led workshops for girls leaving the care system
2020	Holloway Prison – community arts project/documentary	£4,450	Award Report
2021	Unikuir LGBTI+ – Turkey – capacity building for intersectional feminism	£6,558	Application Form (Nov 2020); Award Report -
2021	Colectiva La Revuelta Feminista (Argentina)*	USD4,772.90 in final report (£ award amount not on website)	Application Form; Award Acceptance Form; Award Report (07112021) with Budget and expenses. Ongoing – FRT funded early phase. Hotline, legal research, implementation of new abortion law
2021	Sindihogar/Sindillar (Barcelona) Union of Domestic and Migrant workers* ** This project was added to funding analysis as Award Report was shared. Only project added after Jan 2021 cutoff point	£5,000	Award Report incl. Budget and photos; invoices (10112021); leaflet of launch event. Anti-racist and feminist walking tour of Barcelona, development and piloting
2021	Al Anwar Centre – SDC Haifa **The cutoff point for this review was April 2021 for funding analysis	£6,840	Award Report (07092022); Budget; photos. Not found on FRT website; refurb of meeting place

ANNEX 2 – Interviews Conducted

The Trustees of Feminist Review Trust 2023

1. Prof. Dorothy (Dot) Griffiths
2. Leila Alodaat
3. Prof. Avtar Brah
4. Laura Carter
5. Dr Helen Crowley
6. Dr Joanna Pares Hoare
7. Nicola Simpson
8. Prof. Ann Whitehead
9. Mandy Wright
10. Dr Keina Yoshida

Grantees

Name	Position	Organization
Mary-Ann Stephenson	Director	Women's Budget Group
Sally Etheridge	Programme Lead	Leicester Mammias
Prof. Katherine O'Donnell	University College Dublin	Justice for Magdalenes Research
Irene Staunton	Publisher, Weaver Press	Zimbabwe feminist books project

ANNEX 3 – Guiding Questions for Interviews

Exercise on Lessons Learned at the Feminist Review Trust

Your Engagement

- What has been your role in the Trust?
- How and when did you get involved?
- What motivated or encouraged you to get involved and to stay involved?

Evolution of mission and management of the Trust

- Can you describe key moments in the evolution of the mission and focus of the Trust?
- What intention or insight guided that evolution?
- Why did the FRT decide to focus on 'difficult-to-fund' projects? What was the intention behind this? What was the problem you were trying to address?

How did 'systems' evolve at the Trust?

- Setting up and managing calls for applications?
- Criteria for funding/selection of grantees?
- Decision-making and follow-up with grantees?
- Reporting of implementation/impact and use of funding?

Governance of the FRT

- How did governance evolve at the Trust given the unique structure of the *Feminist Review* journal and the FRT Board of Trustees?
- Were there always representatives of the journal on the Board of Trustees for the FRT?
- How did the relationships evolve?
- What were the benefits of the unique structure of the Trust?
- What were the challenges of the unique structure of the Trust?
- Intention behind this? What was the problem you were trying to address?
- What lessons can be learned from operating such a hybrid structure that may be useful to new funders in this area?

Volunteerism as a principle and practice at the Trust

- How important was the volunteering nature of the running of the Trust? – is it a point of principle? Pragmatism? Both?
- What were the benefits?
- What were the challenges?
- What further support could have been given to volunteers?
- What lessons do you think can be drawn from this that might be useful to other funders of feminist causes?

Understanding theories of change of the Trust and the projects it funded

- What were the typical durations of FRT grants? What range?
- What was the typical level of funding offered of FRT? What range?
- How would you describe the range and type of grantees that the Trust supported?

What were the expectations of change/transformation by the FRT through its grants?

Was there an expectation of social/feminist change through the projects that were supported?

Would you consider grants to be catalytic in terms of pump priming or paving the way for larger changes or for wider support to a project FRT has funded? Can you give me an example?

Were considerations of survival of a group or initiative part of the rationale for support? e.g. emergency support or life support to prevent it from dying/failing? How far was this a marker of success for the Trust?

How far was sustainability of projects considered, i.e. the aim or intention that they would last beyond the funding of the Trust or contribute to longer-term change processes in the organisations/groups?

How would you describe the 'appetite for risk' by the FRT in the selection of grantees?

- in terms of the type of change being supported through the projects?
- in terms of the likelihood of the monies being well spent and accounted for?
- what, for you, did success look like in terms of a 'good project' or 'successful project' supported by the Trust?

Can you highlight 3 projects that stood out for you in terms of potential for change and making a difference?

Finally – Legacy and Lessons

- How would you like the mission and contribution of the FRT to be remembered? What would the headstone say??!
- Do you see a need for new and continued funding to feminist actions and causes? Why?
- What advice would you give to a new generation of activists seeking to fund change?
- What insights would you like to share with them?

Questions to Grantees

- How did you learn about the Trust? Why did you apply?
- What was your experience of engaging with the Trust?
- How important/ relevant are small grants like the FRT to your work?
- How do you see the current state of feminist funding and grassroots funding?
- How can grassroots funding be promoted and supported?

Eleanor O’Gorman

Dr Eleanor O’Gorman is currently Deputy Director at the Intellectual Forum, Jesus College, Cambridge, and Senior Associate at the University of the Cambridge Centre for Gender Studies. Following her PhD at Cambridge focussing on global security from a gender perspective, Eleanor had a passionately engaging international career working on aid, conflict and peacebuilding.

Early on, she worked as a Senior Adviser with the United Nations in New York and Brussels working on crisis prevention and recovery issues. She was also a director at a peacebuilding NGO in London, and a freelance adviser to many governments, NGOs, and international organisations. Her country experience includes Democratic Republic of Congo, Liberia, Zimbabwe, Somalia, Timor-Leste, Lebanon, Sri Lanka and Nepal as well as regular assignments on policy and strategy with headquarter teams in New York, Geneva and Brussels.

A significant element of Eleanor’s work focused on feminist peace and funding, taking a gender and power perspective on the impact of war, violence, politics and aid on the lives of women and girls. She led major reviews on these issues with UN agencies, and with NGOs including WILPF.

Teaching and mentoring remain part of Eleanor’s work since from her very first job as lecturer of politics and development at UEA in Norwich back in the 1990s. She takes a particular interest in working with postgraduate and mature students. She is the author of *Conflict and Development* with Zed Books, London and *The Frontline Runs Through Every Woman: Women and Local Resistance in the Zimbabwean Liberation War* with James Currey Publishers.